

UNVEILING THE EXPERIENCES OF MASTER TEACHERS IN THE CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT: A QUALITATIVE RESEARCH STUDY

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Unveiling the Experiences of Master Teachers in the Curriculum Development: A Qualitative Research Study

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Abstract

This study explored the experiences of Master Teachers in Koronadal City Division in curriculum development to capture their practices and understanding of the phenomenon. This study specifically delved into the lived experiences of the Master Teachers, their contexts of lived experiences, their ways in navigating challenges and constraints, and their views in the curriculum development. The study employed a transcendent qualitative research approach, mainly the phenomenological method in inquiry. Also, this phenomenological study followed the procedure proposed by Moustakas (1994) for the analysis. Findings of the study revealed eminent themes that encapsulate the master teachers' crucial part in curriculum development and other contributors in the community. Exploration on the experiences of master teachers have emerged the themes on living their roles as essential in curriculum development and educative process, context of teachers in curriculum development on support and resources, challenges navigated and mechanisms in resolving constraints, and views and insights of master teachers in curriculum development. These experiences impart salient perspectives in curriculum development which advance the idea that their duties are critical and relevant in making the curriculum inclusive and contextualized to learners in the community. Thus, the essence of their experiences in curriculum development transcends from their roles to their life goals and aspirations to establish profound contributions in the schools and the entire learning community.

Keywords: *curriculum development, lived experiences, master teachers*

Introduction

Clear learning objectives, successful teaching and learning, and ensuring the caliber of learning process in the Department of Education all depend on the design and development of a curriculum. In order to create a cohesive and efficient curriculum, educators, administrators, and subject matter experts—particularly master teachers—work together at the institutional level. Master instructors are the foremost authorities on curriculum design and execution due to their depth of experience and wealth of pedagogical knowledge. Their knowledge and experiences provide insightful viewpoints on the challenging task of developing powerful educational frameworks.

Curriculum development is a process providing a means for ordering and directing learning experiences, allowing certain educational aims to be realized at school level which continually undergoes review, revision, and constant change. Consequentially, curriculum development can be challenging, therefore the involvement of all stakeholders, especially individuals who are directly involved in student instruction, are a vital piece in successful curriculum development and revision. In view of this, teachers play a central role in curriculum development with their knowledge, experiences and competencies, teachers are central to any curriculum development effort (Alsubaie, 2016; Li et al., 2020).

Master teachers are experienced educators who play a crucial role in school. They typically have a strong track record of effective teaching and provide leadership to support teachers in school. To provide the need of teachers and guide for effective learning for the learners in school, master teachers should mentor and serve as instructional leader in the curriculum development of the department.

In the context, curriculum development has posed critical challenges to Master Teachers of Koronadal City Division specifically establishing the learning recovery measures after the years of school closure due to the pandemic. As it is deemed necessary, teachers and master teachers in the division are instructed to get involved in strengthening and intensifying the curriculum implementation and contextualization in order to resolve the learning loss of thousands of learners. Consequentially, the prevalence of challenges such as implementing numerous programs from the central office, master teachers' capability to utilize advanced technological ICT tools, and the involvement in curriculum designing, planning, and delivery are some of the issues these teachers encounter.

Therefore, this study intends to explore the lived experiences of master teachers in Koronadal City Division in terms of their roles in curriculum development, exposing the various issues with the department's curriculum, illuminating the difficulties they encounter, and the significance of their contributions in the department. This study also aims to delve into understanding the context of their lived experiences, challenges and constraints, and their views in curriculum development.

Research Questions

This study aimed to delve into the experiences of master teachers in curriculum development and analyze these experiences to derive themes to understand the phenomenon. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the Master Teachers in Koronadal City Division in curriculum development?

2. What are the contexts of lived experiences of master teachers in the curriculum development?
3. How do master teachers navigate challenges and constraints in curriculum development?
4. What are the views of master teachers in the curriculum development?

Methodology

Research Design

The present study adopted a transcendental qualitative research approach, mainly the phenomenological method in inquiry. Qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involves collection of data from participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of the data in which a structurally flexible final report will be written (Creswell, 2014). In addition, it is a form of social action that stresses the way people interpret and make sense of their experiences to understand the social reality of individuals (Mohajan, 2018).

This study constituted a transcendental phenomenological method to explore the experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development in the Koronadal City Division. In phenomenological research, the researcher describes the structure of the experience based on reflection and interpretation of the research participant's story (Moustakas, 1994). A phenomenological approach to inquiry is fundamentally grounded in the consciousness of the individual which aims to see learning strictly from the point-of-view of the individual as an immediate state in consciousness and as an intentional expression of self in the world (Creely, 2018).

Moreover, a phenomenology is an ideal qualitative methodology for exploring the meaning of lived-experience (Shaw & Conelly, 2012). The aim of this phenomenological research was to determine what the experience means for the people who have had the experience of the phenomenon and to arrive at the general meanings. This research design was found appropriate to attain the purpose of the current research and to arrive to a certain conclusion of the phenomenon.

Participants

The participants of this study were the Master Teachers in Koronadal City Division. This study used purposeful sampling technique in selecting the teacher-participants for the study. In addition, a set of criteria was composed for the purposeful selection process of the participants that was based on the attributes and experience of the participants that can provide information-rich accounts for the purpose of this study. The researcher purposefully determined the participants from the eight school districts in Koronadal City Division that have rich experience in curriculum development.

With that said, the inclusion criteria being considered in the selection of the participants are as follows: (a) must be a Master Teacher stationed in Koronadal City Division, (b) must be assigned in an elementary school in Koronadal City Division, (c) has served at least ten years as master teacher, (d) must have outstanding performance ratings for at least three years, and (e) must have rich experiences in curriculum development. Most importantly, sample participants have willingness to participate in the study which was highly considered.

Instrument

The study utilized a set of interview questionnaire to delve the lived experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development. The interview questionnaire was composed of questions that relates to the experiences of the teachers in curriculum planning, designing, and development as well as its implementation. Importantly, the instrument have undergone validation process to ensure its validity and guarantee purposeful conduct of interview sessions with the participants.

Procedure

This phenomenological study followed the procedure proposed by Moustakas (1994). The procedure entails the selection of the participants after setting the criteria. Then, the researcher obtained informed consent from the participants, should be informed with the purpose of the study, and agree with the setting and time element in the conduct of the study. The researcher also ensured the confidentiality among the participants with the conduct of the study.

In collecting the data, the researcher engaged in the epoche process as a way of creating an atmosphere and rapport for conducting the interview, bracket the question, and conduct the qualitative research interview to obtain descriptions of the experience of the master teachers in curriculum development.

To initialize the process, the researcher developed criteria for selecting participants, establish contract, obtain informed consent, insure confidentiality, agree to place and time commitments, and obtain permission to record and publish. After which, the researcher developed instructions and guiding questions or topics needed for the phenomenological research interview. The step was followed by developing individual textural and structural descriptions, composite textural and composite structural descriptions, and a synthesis of textural and structural meanings and essences of the experience.

For the summary, implications and outcomes, the researcher summarized the entire study, relate study findings to and differentiate

from findings of literature review, relate study to possible future research and develop an outline for a future study, and also relate study to personal outcomes, professional outcomes, social meanings and relevance, and offer closing comments as to researcher's future direction and goals that enriched the purpose of this study.

Generally, the findings from the analysis generated perspectives to the experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development. This purpose directs the understanding of the essences of these experiences for further cultivation of empirical knowledge that are essential in drawing implications.

Ethical Considerations

The role of the researcher as teacher was assumed through informing, developing a knowledge, assisting the progress of competence, and helping facilitate learning of other individuals. The researcher taught the readers how are these experiences of master teachers similar with other experiences in the new normal education.

The researcher also took role as an advocate to carry the essence of the master teachers' experiences based on the findings, how these findings might be generalized, and accommodate theoretical discourse regarding with the findings. Thus, as an advocate, the researcher sanitized the approaches as the readers may take it as a counterpart of the study. Moreover, the researcher recognized some invalidities made by the observational interpretations of the phenomenon described in this study. In such way, the researcher may provide best counter arguments which posed against the constructed assertions.

Importantly, the researcher recognized that interpretations vary in relation to unique perspective and experience of each other as it is relative to their credibility and utility. As the readers derive their own meaning as a unique individual, the researcher as a relativist should consider that differences are present in every aspect of existence. Therefore, the researcher made ethical choices in accommodating these varying perspectives and interpretation in undertaking processes in the research to establish acceptability of the research findings.

Since this is a qualitative study, ethical issues are inevitably present and must be addressed to increase the potential of validity of the paper. In conducting this case study, the researcher considered and constituted protocols in order to secure ethical and social aspects of the research undertakings. The researcher secured an approval from the Koronadal City Division Office and the schools in which the participants are employed to conduct the study.

One potential issue is the submission and willingness of the participants to participate in the study. In such, letters of invitation to participate were sent among the identified participants of the study and the researcher informed the participants with the purpose of the study. Since the responses were recorded, the researcher asked the participants' consents for that matter to be used for the analysis and interpretation, assuring that these were held with utmost confidentiality.

The participants were also informed with their role in the study, the level of their involvement, and there should be no personal interest of the researcher to any qualitative personal accounts were committed.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the description of participants and the findings of the study on the lived experiences of master teachers in curriculum development, their context, their navigation of challenges and constraints, and their views on curriculum development.

Description of Participants

Hereunder are the descriptions of the participants who were involved in this study of whom were master teacher in Koronadal City Division.

Participant 1

Participant 1 is a master teacher -II of a central elementary school in the middle of the city. She was one of the oldest master teachers in Koronadal City Division. She is 57 years of age and served 27 years as master teacher-I and 10 years as master teacher II in Koronadal City Division. She is a promising and dedicated master teacher in school. She introduced some innovations in the division like how to make Daily Lesson Plan for new teachers, DLL for the old and Learning Activity Sheets or LAS. She loves to teach children that's why her knowledge and skills are more effective and adopted by her colleagues.

In her 27 years as master teacher he produced more graduates in her school. She assesses her colleagues and helped them to be an effective teacher. In addition, participant 1 was a facilitator in many trainings like in the curriculum development and trainings for teaching methods and strategies. She design a lot of activities to support the curriculum and implement this aspect for the school children.

Participant 1 engaged in the community activities like in reading and numeracy activities. She made herself busy to support the children and follow u the learning activities around her school. She even conducted home visitation every Friday to make sure that the learners are participating the planned activities. Participant 1 is an active master teacher in her age. She was really dedicated and effective educator of the learners.

Participant 2

Participant 2 is a male master teacher in baryo Central School in Koronadal City. He is 31 years of age and he has been in teaching for 7 years. He has been a master teacher for two years. Participant 2 experienced conflict of many reports and overload in teaching as master teacher in his school. He embraced many challenges in terms of curriculum development. As master teacher he did very well in his responsibilities like checking of lesson plan everyday and observed and facilitate teachers through guiding their instruction in the classroom. Furthermore, Participant 2 conducted and served speaker or facilitator in the School Learning Action Cell or SLAC sessions. He helped teacher to equip and enhance knowledge in terms of the different strategies and techniques in teaching.

Participant 2 also offers his support in extending technical assistance to his colleagues whenever help is needed in the workplace most especially in the curriculum development, in assessment of the different programs like in reading and numeracy. He also designed some trainings and activities in school. He taught and guided the teachers in terms of ICT concerns. Participant 2 is truly a master teacher because he served a role model not only to the workplace but in the community.

Participant 3

Participant 3 is a master teacher in baryo School in Koronadal City. She is 55 years of age and she has been in teaching for 25 years. She has been a master teacher for 4 years. Participant 3 experienced challenges in ICT and overload in teaching as master teacher in her school. She embraced many challenges in terms of curriculum development. She is also School Action Cell coordinator in her school. Furthermore, Participant 3 conducted and served speaker or facilitator in the School Learning Action Cell or SLAC sessions. She helped teacher to equip and enhance knowledge in terms of the different strategies and techniques in teaching.

Participant 3 supervises the different programs in the school also offers his support in extending technical assistance to his colleagues whenever help is needed in the workplace most especially in the curriculum development, in assessment of the different programs like in reading and numeracy. He also designed some trainings and activities in school. He taught and guided the teachers in terms of ICT concerns. Participant 2 is truly a master teacher because he served a role model not only to the workplace but in the community.

Participant 4

Participant 4 is a master teacher -I of a central elementary school in the middle of the city. She is 45 years of age and served 4 years as master teacher-I in Koronadal City Division. She is also promising and dedicated master teacher in school. She introduced some innovations in the division like how to make Daily Lesson Plan for new teachers, DLL for the old and Learning Activity Sheets or LAS. In her 20 years as classroom teacher she produced more graduates in her school. She assesses her colleagues and helped them to be an effective teacher. In addition, participant 4 was a facilitator in many trainings like in the curriculum development and trainings for teaching methods and strategies. She also designed a lot of activities to support the curriculum and implement this aspect for the school children.

Participant 4 is active in the community activities like in reading and numeracy activities. She made herself busy to support the children and follow up the learning activities around her school. She conducted home visitation once a month to make sure that the learners are participating in the planned activities.

Participant 5

Participant 5 is a journalist. She is 50 years of age and master teacher -I 5 years in central elementary school in the middle of the city. She wrote and published some articles and teaching materials. She innovated learning materials every year. She is a promising and dedicated master teacher in school. She introduced some innovations in the division like how to make Daily Lesson Plan for new teachers, DLL for the old and helped them through the use of ICT in their lessons. In her 5 years as master teacher he produced more competitive graduates. She assesses her colleagues and helped them to be an effective teacher. In addition, participant 5 was a facilitator in many trainings like in the curriculum development and trainings for teaching methods and strategies. She design a lot of activities to support the curriculum and implement this aspect for the school children.

Participant 1 engaged in the community activities like in reading and numeracy activities. She made herself busy to support the children and follow up the learning activities around her school. She even conducted home visitation every Friday to make sure that the learners are participating in the planned activities. Participant 1 is an active master teacher in her age. She was really dedicated and effective educator of the learners.

Major Findings

This section discusses the findings of study with the analysis and interpretations of the themes generated from qualitative accounts.

Experiences of Master Teachers in the Curriculum Development

The analysis of the participants' experiences has drawn five major themes that describes the experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development and its implications to the educative process. These emergent themes elaborate the experiences, perspectives, and insights of the master teacher in curriculum development in terms of teachers' roles, context of their experiences, navigated challenges and mechanisms in resolving constraints, and their views.

Table 1 presents the thematic analysis as the qualitative findings in this study.

The findings of the study encapsulate the experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development as delved through qualitative methods. As emergent themes highlight the participants' experiences, it can be inferred that their lived experiences and context of their experiences revolve in their roles as master teachers and their initiatives to leverage curriculum development and implementation through stakeholder's participation and involvement.

Moreover, unprecedented challenges and constraints are present as they navigate on their responsibilities, hence, mechanisms to resolve these concerns were initialized to approach challenges with the most feasible means through resourcefulness and time management.

Table 1. *Thematic Analysis*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
A	Work-related challenges and constraints Perceptions to roles of stakeholders in curriculum development Professional development for teachers as intervention to maximize role in curriculum development Role of teachers in curriculum development Time management to resolve challenges	Living their Roles as Essential in Curriculum Development and Educative Process
B	Presence of challenges and constraints Significance of stakeholders' participation in curriculum development through collaboration and established linkages Critical roles of teachers in curriculum development Upskilling of teacher competence Views and perspectives	Context of Teachers in Curriculum Development: Support and Resources
C	Pressing challenges in the workplace Stakeholders' support and active involvement Means to support curriculum	Challenges Navigated and Mechanisms in Resolving Constraints
D	Challenges in the workplace Collaboration with the stakeholders as an essential aspect in curriculum development Teacher's vital contributions in curriculum development Ways in resolving challenges	Views and Insights of Master Teachers in Curriculum Development
E	Challenges and constraints in curriculum implementation Approaches in ensuring quality of curriculum Mechanisms in resolving challenges Collaboration as an important aspect in curriculum development Support to teachers' professional development	

Living their Roles as Essential in Curriculum Development and Educative Process

The exploration on the lived experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development highlighted their essential roles as they are vital in ensuring the quality of delivering and implementing the curriculum in educative process and how these experiences shaped their understanding of curriculum development. The following statements describe their experiences:

My personal values and beliefs play a significant role in shaping my approach to building partnerships in curriculum development. I believe in the power of collaboration and the importance of valuing diverse perspectives. This belief guides me to actively seek input from parents, teachers, and community members, ensuring that their voices are heard and incorporated into the curriculum... (2, 18a)

Well, in the context of curriculum development, effective collaboration with stakeholders often involves respecting diverse perspectives, promoting inclusivity, and prioritizing educational outcomes that benefit students... (4, 17a)

...However, there is also a strong belief in the importance of community and collaboration, which can facilitate curriculum development by encouraging a more inclusive and participatory approach. To work within this context, I strive to strike a balance between honoring cultural traditions while also promoting innovative teaching methods that prioritize critical thinking and creativity...(2, 30)

From these statements it can be inferred that master teachers foster collaboration in order to operationalize key players in curriculum development and as how these individuals such as the internal and external stakeholders engage in educative process. Additionally, as mater teachers, their role in providing development programs to their colleagues is essential in ensuring the quality implementation of curriculum. These can be assumed from the following statements:

...I plan to prioritize professional development programs for teachers, providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively engage students in their learning journey. These initiatives align with DepEd's mission and objectives of ensuring access to quality education and empowering learners to become productive members of society. By equipping teachers with modern teaching strategies, we can create a dynamic learning environment that fosters critical thinking, creativity, and holistic development among students. (2, 38)

...professional development opportunities, and creating a culture that values their input. In addition, establishing regular feedback channels, involving teachers in curriculum planning committees, and providing resources for continuous training empower educators to contribute effectively. Acknowledging their expertise and encouraging innovation fosters a sense of ownership, leading to more dynamic and student-centric curriculum development. (4, 31b)

Their experiences in performing their roles as master teachers have also presented notions in building connections to colleagues and superiors through effective communication and recognizing the distinction of each one. Through these facets, it can help ensure the effectiveness of the process in curriculum development as various key individuals are concerned. This synthesis is explicated in the following statements:

However, in the long run, I learned how to manage different behaviors by building strong relationships and making sure that my supervisor might not be offending on their part. Acknowledging their worth and wisdom and being open with their ideas also helped a lot to have good communication among the team. (2,14)

..Building strong relationship and being open to new practices are also the contributing factors for the success of curriculum development. These strategies are effective because they promote collaboration and continuous learning, allowing teachers to address challenges and constraints more effectively. Additionally, by adapting the curriculum, master teachers can ensure that it is engaging and relevant for their students, leading to improved learning outcomes. (2, 34b)

The lived experiences of master teachers in curriculum development have defined their goals and perspectives in realizing their roles and responsibilities. May they have perceived their roles as essential in curriculum implementation and ensuring quality deliver of educative process, various factors interplay such as their personal values and teaching philosophies, working milieus, and the extent of support from their community.

Context of Teachers in Curriculum Development: Support and Resources

Consequential to the duties and responsibilities of the master teachers in curriculum development, is the need to advance their knowledge and skills in order to develop relevant approaches in delivering instruction and curriculum implementation. In addition, teachers much be provided opportunities for professional development as intervention to maximize role in curriculum development, to upskilling their competence, and advancement to related fields to improve practice. These are ascertained in the following statements:

Every teacher is encouraged to attend professional training not only the school learning action cell. The teachers are monitored and helped by the school head and supervision of master teachers in school... (1, 20)

...seeking professional development opportunities to stay updated on best practices, and adapting curriculum to meet the diverse needs of students...(2, 34b)

The experiences of the master teachers in curriculum development have included the vitality of stakeholders' support and involvement in order to realize the school plan and curricular activities. Through these linkages and partnerships, master teachers are able to strengthen the curriculum planning and implementation which proportionally impact the quality of learning. The collaboration with the stakeholders is perceived essential to modify the curriculum to make it relevant to the needs and diversity of the learners. These insights are generated from the following statements:

I personally include the involvement of stakeholders in the curriculum development of the pupils by providing feedback, insights, and ideas to create a more interactive and adaptable curriculum that meets evolving societal requirements and individual learning needs. By attending quarterly SMEPA, inviting community officials to participate, where they can provide input on how the curriculum aligns with community needs and values. (1, 18)

... When collaborating with stakeholders like parents, teachers, and community members, personal values and beliefs can influence how one approaches and engages in these partnerships. (5, 22)

Collaboration with the stakeholders is considered as an essential aspect in curriculum development as the communities are given the opportunities to share their inputs and insights to improve the quality of the curriculum through making it more socially relevant to learners. Through this collaboration, the pressing needs of the school are shared to the community to find resolutions to establish mutual and shared accountabilities.

Moreover, collaboration with the stakeholders ensures that the learning environment is safe, conducive, and responsive to the needs of the learners. The stakeholders' support definitely safeguard that curriculum development is set into the context of the community to make it inclusive, relevant, and aligned to the current learning conditions. This can be assumed from these accounts:

In promoting curriculum, community members as I observed in my school promotes and provide the curriculum the support for its implementation. They also help to create awareness of the curriculum among parents, students, and community members. The school established a good relationship with stakeholders thus creating an effective education systems and effective learning environments. This is very true as all stakeholders need to come together in a meaningful way thru collaboration and therefore connection. And successful collaboration is seen between all stakeholders and it means deep listening as well as active doing. (1, 26)

The collaboration between public elementary schools, local government units, and other community organizations in improving the curriculum can be described as a dynamic and multi-faceted partnership. These stakeholders work together to ensure that the curriculum is relevant, inclusive, and aligned with the needs of the students and the community. Through regular meetings, consultations, and joint initiatives such as SMEPA, they strive to create a well-rounded educational experience that prepares students for the challenges of the future. Additionally, this collaboration fosters a sense of shared responsibility and collective ownership in shaping the curriculum, ultimately benefiting both the students and the wider community. (2, 26)

Providing opportunities to the stakeholders to get involved in the curriculum development and other activities substantially impact the implementation of school programs to be more effective and efficient. Stakeholders in the locality and teachers' collaboration are also key to continuous improvement and sustainability of the different programs, projects, and activities in the context of the school and community. This can be affirmed in the following statements:

...Additionally, I actively engage with local stakeholders such as parents, community leaders, and educators to ensure that their perspectives are considered in the curriculum development process. (2, 30)

Our Local Government units may provide support through funding, infrastructure, and policy advocacy, while community organizations can contribute expertise, mentorship programs, and extracurricular activities. This collaborative effort ensures that the curriculum reflects the community's values, addresses specific challenges, and promotes a well-rounded education tailored to local contexts. (4, 27)

In our locality, LGU plays an active role in improving the curriculum specifically our BLGU and SGC. They are active during our programs and activities. They also attend in our SPT meeting during the deliberation of the MOOE budget and planning for FY 2024. They are also present during our SMEPA and GPTA meeting. The MLGU on the other hand show their support to the schools supporting the District and Municipal Meet through SEF budget. They are also active every Brigada Eskwela by delivering the needed materials of the school. (3, 30)

Collaboration with the stakeholders substantially contribute to effective and efficient development and implementation of curricular programs. With these potentials, collaboration is considered a school's strength and best practice to ensure school operations, addressing concerns, and sustainability of programs.

Challenges Navigated and Mechanisms in Resolving Constraints

Master Teachers have encountered various challenges in the workplace that potentially pose predicaments in attaining educative goals particularly in curriculum development. The participants experienced these challenges in terms of work pressures and expectation, dealing with the colleagues, and other challenges in implementing curricular activities, which can be derived from these statements:

Pressure from school administrators. Often under a lot of pressure to come up with new teaching strategies and ways in which I can improve pupil learning. Peers and colleagues' expectations of me as their mentor too... (1, 14)

The first challenge that I encountered was dealing with the different behaviors of the teachers especially those who are way older than me. I still had some hesitations in extending my help or correcting their practices at first...2,14)

...adapting to diverse student needs, language barriers. Limited resources, resistance to change (3 sec. post) of seasoned teachers... (4, 21a)

... Time, work overload, lack of fund to the activities as the Master Teacher in my school. Limited resources and time constraints also challenges in effectively carrying out curriculum activities. (5, 36)

Additionally, these challenges significantly are attributed to administrative works, extreme workloads, and responsibilities that cause fatigue and stress among the master teachers in curriculum development. Various tasks that are assigned to Master Teachers make their jobs more complicated and exhausting that consume much of their time and energy. These sentiments are expressed in these statements:

... Another challenge is the time-consuming administrative work that comes with teaching that takes a lot of time in managing pupils, creating assessments and actually teaching lessons Time management is a vital skill actually for me. The overwhelming amount of administrative work that adversely affect my work -life balance, as I require myself to spend time outside of working hours, grading assignments, filling out reports, checking DLL's of my mentees and other more. (5, 14)

Over fatigue and stress really consume me specially during the times that I need to teach and I have advisory class, observe, facilitate SLAC and INSET, submit reports as coordinator in Filipino, LR, SLAC, SBM, and made my reports like grades, TOS and exams, MPS, SF 9 and 10, etc. (3, 17)

Common challenges for as an MT include managing diverse responsibilities, addressing mentees needs, and navigating school tasks. Commitment is one of my motivation that often a stem to foster a positive learning environment... (4, 13a)

Other challenges and constraints are the limited resources and inadequate time as contributed by the over workloads. Further, resources such as funds pose major concerns for the realization and implementation of different programs and activities in school. Master

Teachers experienced these challenges as they render their responsibility in assisting the school administrators to effectively deliver the curricular activities with the involvement of the stakeholders and others. The following are the related accounts of the participants:

...Additionally, limited resources and time constraints also posed challenges in effectively carrying out curriculum activities. (2, 32)

... The lack of fund for the projects, problems about the participation of stakeholders and conflict of time. (3, 36)

Overloading of time in teaching and many paper works are some of them. (4, 35)

... One challenge is time contains and lack of fund for our curriculum... (5, 28)

Significant to this experience of challenges are the coping mechanisms of teachers as their resolves in dealing with these constraints. Time and stress management, collaboration among colleagues, and open communication with colleagues are among these mechanisms master teachers have navigated in order to ensure their sound welfare as they perform their tasks and responsibilities in curriculum development. Also, being resourceful in addressing the different constraints is one of the ways master teachers cope with the challenges they encounter. This can be ascertained from these statements:

Time management, Sir Gudz, need to manage my time. Shall we say wise in term of time. (1, 38)

...Continuous feedback, collaboration among educators, and adapting to emerging educational trends can enhance curriculum development. (4, 21c)

I need to manage my time and always fight stress. Yan ang ginagawa ko. Umiwas sa mga stressful activities. (4, 39)

...We need only to sacrifice our time and effort to support these programs with the help of my school head, my co teachers and stakeholders... (5, 20)

We need also to have good communication and always give positive feedback of what we are facing... (4, 43)

... resource sharing, expertise and professional development, and community engagement and experiential learning... (5, 30)

Resourcefulness. Ito ang aking pamamaraan para ma cope ang need sa curriculum as Master teacher. Kapag walang fund ay maghanap talaga ng paraan at maging resourceful. (5, 38)

The emergent experiences of the master teachers in the curriculum development critically speak on the various challenges and constraints that impede the realization of curriculum development and delivery. Though these constraints are considerably perennial, the education system persevere to provide meaningful resolves in order to aid teachers in the field.

Views and Insights of Master Teachers in Curriculum Development

It is also highlighted from qualitative accounts the significant insights from master teachers on their views in curriculum development. Among their experiences is their crucial impact on curriculum alignment for the delivery of more effective educative process. These insights are reflected in the following statements:

Teachers play a vital role in curriculum development as they bring their expertise, experience, and knowledge of their pupils to shape the curriculum. Teachers provide valuable input in identifying learning objectives, selecting content and designing appropriate instructional strategies for the pupils. (1, 30)

Yes. I believe that as a Master Teacher, I can make a positive impact on young students' lives and contribute to improving the education system. Aside from helping the students, I also see myself mentoring and guiding other teachers, sharing my knowledge and expertise to help them become more effective educators. Additionally, I believe that being a Master Teacher would provide me with the opportunity to advocate for educational reforms and policies that can address the challenges faced by elementary public schools. (2, 36)

Master teachers' role in curriculum development can be considered as one of most important factors to improve the educative process through sharing their expertise and services. Moreover, providing coaching and mentoring activities to colleagues to ensure quality delivery of curriculum are deemed vital to establish collegial collaboration. Strategies and approaches in ensuring the effective development and implementation of curriculum are also managed and initiated. This synthesis is captured from the following statements:

Teachers and school staff play a pivotal role in curriculum development by offering valuable insights into student needs, learning styles, and classroom dynamics. Their involvement can be optimized through collaborative decision-making processes, professional development opportunities, and creating a culture that values their input. In addition, establishing regular feedback channels, involving teachers in curriculum planning committees, and providing resources for continuous training empower educators to contribute effectively. Acknowledging their expertise and encouraging innovation fosters a sense of ownership, leading to more dynamic and student-centric curriculum development. (4, 31a)

... In addition, our school is planning to enhance and to have curriculum mapping and alignment. Align the curriculum across grade

levels or subject areas. This involves analyzing the existing curriculum, identifying gaps or redundancies, and ensuring a coherent and progressive learning experience for students. Curriculum mapping helps ensure that the content, skills, and learning outcomes are aligned with the school's educational objectives... (5, 23)

The experience of the master teachers in performing their roles are significant in terms of engaging themselves to improve the teaching and learning process. Further the insights of the master teachers on their roles encapsulate their major contributions in the alignment and contextualization of curriculum to make it adaptive to the context and needs of the learners.

Also, support for teachers' professional development is deemed essential to improve their competence and qualities as master teachers. Also, opportunities like provision of technical assistance and collaboration with colleagues give impactful avenue for teachers to share practices. This is inferred from these following statements:

As master teacher, my colleagues always ask for TA. Sharing to them what I learn is really fulfilling. Moreover, even now MT play significant role in school by planning and facilitating seminars and workshops not only for the teachers but also for the learners. (3, 55)

... and professional development are the key to improve the curriculum with enough fund. (5, 32b)

... Supervises the teachers and make design for the professional development of my colleagues. (5, 40)

Providing the teachers, the support they need in terms of professional development through different trainings, seminars, and workshops, fundamentally impacts their performance and expertise in curriculum development which presumably affects the quality of their teaching. It can be assumed from the findings that the support to colleagues through technical assistance and provision of professional development opportunities are the foremost responsibilities of the master teachers in the teaching community that they need to undertake with accountability.

Conclusions

This phenomenological study on the experiences of master teachers has revealed eminent themes that encapsulate their crucial part and other contributors in the community in curriculum development. Exploration on experiences of the master teachers have emerged the themes on living their roles as essential in curriculum development and educative process, context of teachers in curriculum development on support and resources, challenges navigated and mechanisms in resolving constraints, and views and insights of master teachers in curriculum development

In a more elaborate context, these experiences transcend their crucial duties and responsibilities in ensuring quality educative process through acknowledging their roles and contributions, and also the challenges and constraints they deal in many aspects of curriculum development. Their experiences also highlight the significance of collaboration with the stakeholders in community as it impacts the effectiveness and efficiency of curriculum implementation.

Views and perceptions of the master teachers are also captured in the study that highlight their insights in curriculum development specially in the context of curriculum development. This study collectively revealed the eminent experiences of master teachers in curriculum development that significantly contribute to curriculum development.

The findings on the exploration of master teachers' experiences in curriculum development imply various significant insights that are useful in the educative process and sustainability of different programs and activities. Through the findings, master teachers will be able to intensify their roles and deepen their sense of responsibility as they are crucial in developing and implementing curriculum and in ensuring that the educative process is delivered effectively and efficiently.

Furthermore, stakeholders will strengthen more their accountability as part of school linkages that allow a more progressive educative process through shared responsibility and additional resource to schools' implementation of curricular activities. Partnership between stakeholders in the community enable the school to sustain different programs, projects, and activities that are key to essential benefits among learners and school administrators.

The experiences of master teachers on curriculum development impart salient perspectives on curriculum development which advance the idea that their duties are crucial and relevant in making the curriculum inclusive and contextualized to learners in the community. Thus, the essence of their experiences in curriculum development transcends from their roles to their life goals and aspirations to establish profound contributions in the learning institutions.

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